

D2.2 First short report of cluster events

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Keywords	ECS, citizen science, cluster event, stakeholder engagement, higher education, university

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0.6	26.07.2023	Florence Gignac (SD)	Final edits based on second review
1.0	27.07.2023	Florence Gignac (SD)	Final version ready for submission

List of acronyms

Acronym	Expansion
CS	Citizen science
EC	European Commission
ECS	European Citizen Science
ECSA	European Citizen Science Association
ERA	European Research Area
EU	European Union
HEIs	Higher education institutions
T	Task
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

The 'First short report of cluster events' is Deliverable 2.2 (D2.2) from the EU-funded project European Citizen Science. This deliverable is part of WP2 entitled 'Strengthening links and collaboration', which has the overall objective to strengthen and expand the citizen science community.

More specifically, this deliverable is part of Task 2.5 'Strengthening collaboration through harnessing resources and outputs from EU, national and regional CS initiatives' and focuses on one of the activities of T2.5, which is to organise yearly online cluster events involving projects, networks and European Commission representatives to engage in discussions centred around a unifying theme in the field of CS.

The purpose of this document is to highlight the key insights gathered from the first annual cluster event, which took place online on July 3rd, 2023. The event, titled "Foster the Higher Education Sector in Europe: The role of citizen science in transforming universities", attracted approximately 108 attendees across Europe. Key points for maximising the potential of CS in higher education included raising researchers' awareness of CS, encouraging peer learning, promoting multi-level collaborations, and integrating CS early in education. There was a strong call for supporting early-career researchers, re-evaluating how their contributions to CS are recognised, and developing strategies to drive citizen engagement in CS activities supported by structures within universities. The significance of engaging a broader range of stakeholders, especially those from the university's local ecosystems, was also emphasised.

The document is presented in the following order:

Section 1 introduces the rationale and the objectives of the cluster event. Section 2 elaborates on eight key takeaways of the cluster

event drawn from the experiences of the participating projects and initiatives, and three group activities. Finally, section 3 gathers some concluding remarks and next steps. The annexes include a detailed agenda of the event, details of the projects presented along with the biographies of the speakers, details about the profile of the attendees and a selection of visual output resulting from the activities carried out throughout the event.

1. Cluster event rationale

1.1. Context

1.1.1. The European effort in transforming universities

The European Commission (EC) recognises that higher education institutions (HEIs), in all their various forms, occupy a unique position at the crossroads of education, research, and innovation (EC, 2022a). HEIs serve as spaces where European citizens can gain the important knowledge, skills, competences, and attitudes to navigate future societal, economic, and labour market changes. This unique position enables HEIs to be important players in tackling significant societal challenges and shaping resilient and sustainable economies, thereby nurturing a greener, more inclusive European Union (EU). Acknowledging this, the EC unveiled a strategy in early 2022 to empower and support the higher education system within the EU (EC, 2022a; Council Resolution 2021/C 66/01, 2021). The objective was to strengthen this sector to better respond to the changing needs of society and the economy. The strategy is rooted in “supporting and enabling universities to adapt to changing conditions, to thrive and to contribute to Europe’s resilience and recovery” (EC, 2022a). As part of this overarching strategy, the European Research Area (ERA) incorporated a dedicated initiative, known as Action 13, into its 2022-2024 policy agenda (EC, 2021). This action was specifically created to empower HEIs.

1.1.2. The role of citizen science in the higher education sector

Looking at the EC's policy focus on HEIs, several themes, such as addressing societal needs and sustainability issues, resonate well with benefits observed in the sphere of citizen science (CS). Indeed, according to Hitchcock, Vance-Chalcraft and Aristeidou (2021), who authored the editorial for a special collection on Citizen Science in Higher Education, published in the journal *'Citizen Science: Theory and Practice'*, the inclusion of CS in HEIs represents a valuable way to boost student engagement with the world. The authors suggest that incorporating CS into higher education can lead to improved student learning outcomes and skill acquisition, touching upon diverse areas such as biodiversity, technology, and scientific research in general. Therefore, CS could help transform the higher education system to better address societal needs and sustainability issues with the active participation of citizens and societal engagement. While the widespread integration of CS into HEIs and academic culture is still in its early stages, an increasing number of universities are exploring CS as a mean to engage the public in scientific research, to teach science (or the scientific process) and promote alternative avenues of knowledge creation (Wyler and Haklay, 2018).

1.2. Objectives

In this context, the European Citizen Science (ECS) project, an initiative that fosters a vibrant CS community, sought to provide a space for exchanging hands-on experiences in integrating and using CS practices and activities in universities. To facilitate this, ECS coordinated an online event designed to welcome a wide spectrum of participants. The event aimed to attract academics, educators, university staff, CS practitioners, early-career researchers, policy makers, civil servants, representatives from industry, and members of the general public. The event served as a platform for attendees to learn about, discuss, and reflect on ways to fully harness the power of CS within the higher education sector.

The online event took place on July 3rd 2023 (for programme schedule and list of invited speakers and their corresponding projects, refer to the Annex A and Annex B). The key objectives of this event were to:

- **Network** with the ECS community, European CS community, including large scale CS projects and local CS initiatives, but also academics, early-career researchers, CS practitioners and EC representatives.
- **Learn** about different CS initiatives and their experiences in integrating and organising CS activities in universities.
- **Find** solutions to overcome experienced challenges to support CS initiatives in universities.
- **Discuss** ideas of incentives or measures needed for effectively integrating CS into universities' education and research activities.
- **Explore** ways for early-career researchers to engage further with CS.

This present report compiles takeaway messages for all stakeholders involved, directly or indirectly, in this subject, outlining ways of maximising the potential of CS in higher education.

2. Key takeaways on maximising the potential of CS in higher education

This year's ECS Cluster event delved into the nexus of CS and the higher education landscape. It featured an array of perspectives from a diverse set of stakeholders, including CS practitioners, early-career researchers, university staff, representatives from the EC and university alliances (see Annex C). The event was structured around shared experiences from various initiatives during the morning session, while the afternoon was dedicated to insightful group activities. From these discussions, eight key takeaway messages were distilled on how to fully harness the potential of CS within the higher education sector.

These insights are intended to be useful to a broad spectrum of stakeholders, not confined to any specific group but encompassing all those engaged in CS, education, research, and beyond. However, we recognise that the relevance of these takeaways may vary based on the local context of the reader, where CS is either somewhat well-established or yet to gain a foothold.

Takeaway #1: Raising awareness of CS among researchers within HEIs

A challenge faced by structures supporting CS within universities and research centres that was repeatedly mentioned during the event is that researchers often remain unaware of the potentialities of CS. This represents a significant obstacle hindering the integration of CS within HEI. Three facets of this challenge were discussed by the attendees, along with strategies that could potentially boost the integration of CS within HEI.

- **First, researchers may be unsure about how to incorporate or utilise CS in their research activities.** Hence, it would be advantageous to frequently conduct information sessions geared towards researchers and others at universities interested in setting a CS help desk. These sessions should showcase best practices, demonstrate how other universities or research centres are implementing CS, and illustrate successful CS initiatives, projects, and activities. CS practitioners operating outside the higher education ecosystem should adopt a proactive stance in reaching out to universities and inviting key members to join their CS communities and events.

- **Second, researchers may exhibit a level of scepticism towards research involving citizens, partially due to concerns about the quality of data procured from citizen-led efforts.** In that aspect, efforts should be made to understand the obstacles deterring researchers from embracing CS. Additionally, raising awareness among researchers about the increasing evidence that data gathered through CS can make high-quality contributions comparable to expert-collected data is essential. A compelling example is the direct contribution of certain CS-derived data to the monitoring of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (Fraisl et al., 2022; Fraisl et al., 2020).
- **Third, further exacerbating the situation is a confusion regarding the distinctions between terms such as CS, public engagement, science communication, responsible research and innovation, and scientific divulgation and dissemination.** Therefore, it is crucial that communication is clear, customised and resonates with researchers. This might involve enlisting a scientific communicator who speaks the researchers' language.

Takeaway #2: Exchanging experiences and learning from peers, particularly within a HEIs network

Building upon the first key takeaway, the importance of sharing successful experiences and lessons learned in CS projects is paramount. The benefits of such shared learning experiences are magnified when executed within a strong and coordinated network such as within university alliances. This concept was illustrated by three initiatives participating at the cluster event:

- **INCENTIVE:** In this initiative, CS Hubs were established within four European universities. These hubs did more than merely facilitate CS activities; they spawned a network that promoted a robust exchange of knowledge, experiences, and best practices among these universities. Sharing these success stories not only inspires but also provides practical blueprints for others aiming to integrate CS into their institutions.
- **EUTOPIA-TRAIN:** This initiative established a CS-focused community of practice that fostered peer learning and training within EUTOPIA, a university alliance. More specifically, they prepared “CS clinics” in order to offer researchers of all stages essential resources to comprehend CS, understand its potential, learn how to design and implement a CS project and network with the community.
- **SMART-ER:** Echoing the approach of EUTOPIA-TRAIN, SMART-ER endeavoured to build a robust CS community within the European Consortium of Innovative Universities (ECIU), which is another university alliance in Europe. For instance, they organised webinars to highlight cutting-edge CS projects underway in the various universities within the ECIU Consortium. These webinars served as a platform for addressing common challenges, discussing topics of interest, and finding opportunities for potential joint initiatives. This approach not only fostered a sense of community but also helped identify synergies that could be leveraged for pilot projects.

Takeaway #3: Seeking multi-level synergies among stakeholders to stimulate CS activities in universities

Fostering CS activities within universities is not a solitary endeavour. Instead, it demands the concerted participation and synchronised effort of a multitude of stakeholders, setting in motion a virtuous cycle that

advances CS within HEIs. As such, substantial institutional support at multiple tiers, encompassing the EU, national, regional, and local levels, is needed. Equally critical is the role of key figures within the university – such as CS officers, researchers and mentors. They provide guidance and create an enabling environment that encourages the growth and implementation of CS. The synergy between external institutional support and internal guidance can propel the growth of CS in the higher education landscape.

Takeaway #4: Integrating CS in primary and secondary schools to foster CS integration in HEIs

An observation made during the cluster event underscores a considerable issue: a majority of early-career researchers have not been previously exposed to the concept of CS before stepping into the university environment. This reality underscores the potential impact primary and secondary schools can have on integrating CS within higher education. A foundation can be laid in CS by engaging primary and secondary school students at the early stages of their academic and scientific journey by incorporating CS activities early into schools' curricula. This early foundation can help streamline CS introduction in higher levels of education. For universities, this early foundation can create a pathway to connect with potential future students and generate interest in the university's scientific initiatives. Seeding CS activities in the early stages of a student's educational journey is thus a long-term investment that can foster a new generation of CS advocates in HEIs.

Takeaway #5: Ensuring connection, training, and recognition for early-career researchers

Early-career researchers occupy a distinct niche within HEIs, warranting dedicated focus and support when talking about integrating CS in higher education. Reflections from the event participants suggested three primary elements for cultivating a supportive environment conducive to their growth and integration with CS:

- **Nurturing a sense of community.** Early-career researchers benefit a lot from opportunities to connect, exchange insights, and collaborate with their colleagues within a network. This feeling of community facilitates problem-solving and the generation of ideas.
- **Providing education and training on CS.** A number of researchers at the onset of their careers may be not aware of the opportunities that CS presents for their work or not familiar with incorporating CS into their research activities. Consequently, it is important to provide training workshops and share resources to provide early-career researchers with the tools and knowledge necessary to navigate CS. Implementing mentorship programmes could further assist early-career researchers in incorporating CS into their projects. This solution aligns with some of the recommendations derived from the Mutual Learning Exercise on "Citizen Science Initiatives - Policy and Practice"¹, notably the recommendation to mainstream CS in education, including its integration into research training for PhDs and Postdocs (EC, 2022b).

¹ Materials of the Mutual Learning Exercise available here:

<https://ec.europa.eu/research-and-innovation/en/statistics/policy-support-facility/psf-challenge/mutual-learning-exercise-citizen-science-initiatives-policy-and-practice>

- **Re-evaluating the traditional metrics of academic success** to include the impacts stemming from the integration of CS in research. This implies a shift from focusing solely on publications to also recognising the significance of CS activities. This change in evaluating academic achievements will help incentivise early-career researchers to engage with CS. This final point is further elaborated in the subsequent takeaway since this issue impacts not just young researchers, but all staff within HEIs in a direct and indirect way.

Takeaway #6: Rethinking how researchers are evaluated according to their involvement in CS

One significant challenge identified during the cluster event is the limited recognition researchers receive when they engage in and use CS activities. This situation underscores the need for a comprehensive shift in how research impact is measured, extending beyond traditional academic productivity indices. Thus, there is a pressing need to rethink evaluation criteria for researchers, especially when evaluating their research engaging CS. Participants at the cluster event suggested potential strategies to navigate this obstacle. In the short term, the creation of a database containing scientific journals open to publishing papers using CS as a methodology was suggested. This could provide an immediate platform for researchers to disseminate their CS-oriented work, thereby increasing its visibility and recognition. The long-term goal, however, should be to adapt institutional assessment mechanisms to appreciate CS activities. This involves updating researcher evaluation criteria at an institutional level to account for their use of CS. It is important to note that these more substantial changes will take time and coordination among various stakeholders. Nonetheless, the ultimate goal is to establish an evaluation system that truly values the unique contributions of researchers engaged with CS.

Takeaway #7: Developing strategies to encourage citizens to seek out CS structures in HEIs

The effective integration of CS structures within HEIs is somewhat reliant on the general public interest and participation in CS. It is not a given that citizens will immediately interact with newly introduced CS structures such as hubs, contact points, or help desks just because they have been established within universities or research centres. In fact, despite their existence, some HEIs may still appear as exclusive spaces for certain groups within the population. These CS structures need active public involvement to function optimally as they become liaisons between the local community and the researchers. Therefore, it is key to strategise ways to attract and encourage citizens to participate in these initiatives. Possible strategies those structure could take to increase engagement can include:

- **Enlisting the help of a communications officer** and creating collaborative relationships with other scientific communication events, such as the European Researcher's Night.
- **Producing informative materials and using creative approaches**, such as setting up an Instagram account to display engaging visuals, recording podcasts, maintaining a blog, or crafting visually appealing brochures, which clearly articulate the importance and objectives of CS, aiming to draw public attention and interest.
- **Executing a thorough local and regional analysis of relevant stakeholders** (e.g. associations, NGOs, industries, public institutions, etc.) to enhance the effectiveness of outreach efforts.

- **Making universities more accessible to the public**, for example, by hosting public events, thus creating welcoming spaces for citizens to engage in CS activities.

Takeaway #8: Engaging with a broader spectrum of stakeholders

Beyond the usual stakeholders committed to advancing CS within HEIs such as CS practitioners, university staff, funding agencies, policy makers, and researchers, it is important to bring other possible contributors into this conversation. Entities from local government bodies, such as municipalities, to public institutions such as public libraries and museums, as well as civic or community groups, can significantly impact propelling CS in a higher academic context. Their involvement can offer diverse perspectives, and broaden the reach and impact of CS activities in the higher education landscape.

3. Conclusion and next steps

This document presents a short report of the first cluster events under T2.5 of WP2 of the ECS project. The objective of this report is to spotlight the takeaways drawn from various presentations and group discussions of the event. These takeaways can serve as a useful resource for a wide range of stakeholders, including CS practitioners, early-career researchers, university staff, and policy makers, who are interested in promoting or integrating CS into higher education. The recording of the event's first part is accessible on the ECSA's youtube channel². Moreover, there will be two additional cluster events for 2024 and 2025. These two upcoming events will coincide with the yearly launch of the eu-citizen.science platform, with new features.

These key takeaways will also be integral in shaping the ECS Academy, which is currently under development. The ECS Academy aims to create high quality resources, activities, and training events designed to enhance the skills and knowledge of CS practitioners, civil society, public authorities, businesses, (in)formal and educational establishments, and research funding and performing organisations.

Furthermore, the ECS community continues to thrive with the ECS Collaboration Group convening monthly to discuss various topics. These recurring meetings serve as a networking, resource-sharing, and support platform for all CS initiatives across EU and beyond. With over 45 diverse initiatives, including both large-scale and smaller projects from different parts of the globe, the group delves into aspects of CS such as impact evaluation, inclusivity, education, and sustainability.

² Link to the recording: [European Citizen Science \(ECS\) first cluster event - YouTube](#)

References

- Council Resolution on a strategic framework for European cooperation in education and training towards the European Education Area and beyond (2021-2030) 2021/C 66/01. (2021). Official Journal, C 66, 1-21. CELEX: [https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32021G0226\(01\)](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32021G0226(01)) [legislation]
- EC (2022a) Higher education: making EU's universities ready for the future through deeper transnational cooperation. https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_22_365
- EC (2022b) European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Haklay, M., Gold, M., Huyse, T. (2022). Mutual learning exercise on citizen science initiatives : policy and practice. First topic report, Introduction and overview of citizen science, Publications Office of the European Union. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/29886>
- EC (2021), Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Directorate A – ERA & Innovation, Unit A.2 – ERA governance and Implementation (2021) European Research Area Policy Agenda – Overview of actions for the period 2022-2024 https://commission.europa.eu/system/files/2021-11/ec_rtd_era-policy-agenda-2021.pdf
- Fraisl, D., Hager, G., Bedessem, B. et al. (2022) Citizen science in environmental and ecological sciences. Nat Rev Methods Primers 2, 64. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43586-022-00144-4>
- Fraisl, D., Campbell, J., See, L. et al. (2020) Mapping citizen science contributions to the UN sustainable development goals. Sustain Sci 15, 1735–1751. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-020-00833-7>
- Hitchcock, C., Vance-Chalcraft, H., & Aristeidou, M. (2021). Citizen Science in Higher Education. Citizen Science: Theory and Practice, 6(1), 22. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5334/cstp.467>
- Wyler, D., & Haklay, M. (2018). Integrating citizen science into university. In M. Haklay, S. Hecker, A. Bowser, Z. Makuch, J. Vogel, & A. Bonn (Eds.), Citizen Science: Innovation in Open Science, Society and Policy (pp. 168–182). UCL Press. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/j.ctv550cf2.18>

Annex A – Detailed agenda of the ECS Cluster Event 2023

Location: Online

Timing (CEST)	Content
PART I	
10.00 - 10.05	Welcome <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Housekeeping rules Introduction about the ECS Cluster Event and the topic of 2023
10.05 - 10.35	Introductory presentations <ul style="list-style-type: none"> European Universities alliances: accelerating change in ERA priorities like citizen science (Stijn Delauré) The European Citizen Science project and its Academy (Claudia Fabó Cartas and Cléa Montanari)
10.35 - 10.40	Energiser activity <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Attendees are asked to mark on a geographical map where they are joining from.
10.40 - 11.10	Testimonies - Unleashing the power of CS <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ECSA Working Group - Citizen Science and Universities (Maria Aristeidou) SMART-ER Project (Fernando Vilariño)
11.10 - 11.15	<i>Coffee break</i>
11.15 - 11.45	Talks showcasing how universities currently perform in CS activities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> INCENTIVE with Dr. Maya van den Berg EUTOPIA-Train with Eline Livémont TIME4CS with Claudia Iasillo
11.45 - 12.00	Q&A Session
12.00 - 13.00	<i>Lunch break</i>
PART II	
13.00 - 13.05	Introduction
13.05 - 13.50	Group activity

Three breakout rooms

ROOM 1: What are the challenges that structures that support citizen science in universities currently face? What are some policies that challenge the incorporation of citizen science in universities? How to overcome them?

Moderated by Claudia Fabó Cartas and Gemma Rodriguez

ROOM 2: What are the incentives or measures (from individual to policy level) needed for effectively integrating citizen science into universities' education and research activities? This room will be linked to the co-creation of a statement by TIME4CS about the transformation of universities.

Moderated by Asya Salnikova, Simon Hoyte, TIME4CS

ROOM 3: How can we create a supportive environment for young researchers to engage with citizen science? What role can universities and research institutions play in supporting and training early-career researchers in citizen science?

Moderated by Ruben Riosa, Stefanie Schuerz and Cléa Montanari

13.50 - 13.55

Coffee break

13.55 - 14.35

Group discussion

Moderators of each group presents the main outcome and discussion of their activity

14.35 - 14.50

Closing remarks with Gabriella Leo

14.50 - 15.00

Acknowledgements

Annex B – Speaker biographies and project details

Project	Representative	Logo	Website
Citizen Science and Universities (ECSA Working group)	Maria Aristeidou	 European Citizen Science Association Working Group	https://www.ecsa.ngo/working-groups/citizen-science-and-universities/
SMART-ER Corresponding university alliance: European Consortium of Innovative Universities (ECIU)	Fernando Vilariño		https://www.eciu.eu/smart-er-for-researchers#agenda
INCENTIVE	Maya van den Berg		https://incentive-project.eu/
EUTOPIA-TRAIN Corresponding university alliance: European Universities Transforming into an Open Inclusive Academy for 2050 (EUTOPIA)	Eline Livémont		https://eutopia-university.eu/english-version/research/eutopia-train
TIME4CS	Claudia lasillo		https://www.time4cs.eu/

Representative	Short bio
Maria Aristeidou	Maria Aristeidou is an Assistant Professor at The Open University. Her influential roles include chairing the Citizen Science and Universities working group of the European Citizen Science Association (ECSA), serving on the editorial board of the journal Citizen Science: Theory and Practice, and co-editing the special issue on Citizen Science in Higher Education. Dr. Aristeidou's expertise lies in designing and evaluating citizen science projects that engage young people and adults in both informal and formal educational settings. Her research delves into the dynamics of engagement and learning in online citizen science initiatives and explores innovative methods to integrate citizen science into university Courses.
Fernando Vilariño	Fernando Vilariño is Associate Director of the Computer Vision Centre and Associate Professor at the Computer Science Department of the Univ. Autònoma de Barcelona, Spain. He lectures in "Machine Learning", "Robotics", and "Models of Open Innovation and Citizen Science". His research is linked to Computer Vision and the Social Impact of AI, and he has led different projects related to the implementation of models of Living Labs in the context of citizen-centric Open Innovation. He is the Research Field Coordinator of the ECIU Community of Citizen Science and coordinates the co-creation process for 3 pilots on Citizen Science at the SMART Project.
Maya van den Berg	Maya van den Berg is based at the University of Twente where she is involved in establishing the university's Citizen Science Hub. Based at the DesignLab, she is managing multidisciplinary Research & Innovation projects bringing science and society while focusing on societal challenges. She has a research background in local policies and climate change and worked in several public authorities prior to academia.
Eline Livémont	Eline Livémont has a background in documentary film distribution (Dalton Distribution – DOCVILLE int. documentary film festival) and communication and media research and teaching (imec-SCMIT – Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB)). To no surprise, her professional trajectory has always been rooted in a great motivation to bring knowledge to a wider society. She currently coordinates the Outreach & Communication department at the vice rectorate of Research of the VUB (Vrije Universiteit Brussel). Together with enthusiastic researchers, teachers, communication specialists and creative minds, Eline and her team try to make a difference in building bridges between science and society. They are dedicated to stimulating scientific literacy, involving citizens in VUB's research and providing training to reach out to the world beyond academia.
Claudia lasillo	Claudia lasillo joined APRE in 2018. She holds a MSc degree in Biotechnology and a PhD in Molecular Biology from Aarhus University, in collaboration with the French IGMM (Institut de Génétique Moléculaire de Montpellier). After the PhD, she studied science communication and public engagement in science activities in the post-graduation course "Life science communication" at La Sapienza, University of Rome, with a specific focus on science journalism and institutional communication. In APRE she works as project manager mainly on science and society relationship related projects. She is experienced in science communication, Open Science, Citizen Science, stakeholder and public engagement, community building and capacity building. Since she has joined APRE she has been involved in several EU funded projects and she is coordinating the H2020 project TIME4CS and the HE projects BlueRev and PATTERN.

Annex C – Profile of registrants and attendees

The event registered a total of 212 participants. Given the shared registration link, the socio-demographic profile of the attendees couldn't be accurately determined. The highest number of attendees was 108 in the first part and about 47 attendees in the second part of the event which included group activities. The majority of the 108 attendees came from Europe, with a few participants from South East Asia and Africa (see collaborative map below).

To the question “Do you have any previous experience with CS?” the 108 attendees responded as follows:

Profile: The profiles that resonated most with the 108 attendees (with the option to select multiple) were:

Profile	Number of attendees*	% of attendees*
Civil society/Non-governmental organisation (international)	12	11.1%
Civil society/Non-governmental organisation (national)	2	1.9%
Civil society/Non-governmental organisation (regional or local)	2	1.9%
Education/training organisation	31	28.7%
General public/citizen	9	8.3%
General public: Learner/student	8	7.4%
Industry or business partner	5	4.6%
Media, journalist or communicator	8	7.4%
Policy-makers, institutions and authorities (EU level)	5	4.5%
Policy-makers, institutions and authorities (international)	1	0.9%
Policy-makers, institutions and authorities (national)	6	5.6%
Research: Early-career researcher	15	13.9%
Research: Participant in a citizen science project/Community researcher	19	17.6%
Research: Scientist or belonging to the research community	41	38.0%
Standardisation bodies	1	0.9%

*The “number of attendees” column reflects the number of responses per attendees. For example, 41 attendees selected “Research: Scientist or belonging to the research community”. The “% of attendees” column reflects the average number of responses per attendees (multiplied by 100). For example, 38% of the attendees selected “Research: Scientist or belonging to the research community”

Annex D – Visual outputs of group activities

What are the challenges structures that support citizen science in universities currently face?

- Lack of awareness of CS among researchers**
 - Andrimo 8d: More information sessions and the involvement of the local ecosystem
 - Andrimo 8d: Inspiring seminars, newsletters
- research funding organizations do not envisage CS (and if they do it is "only" as public engagement)**
 - Andrimo 8d: Some definitions of CS push for more active engagement of citizens and not only focus on science dissemination.
- recognition in researchers' evaluation**
- Lack of funding**
- A lot of researchers do not know the potentiality of CS and how to use it**
 - Andrimo 8d: Starting from scratch in some places. Not "just" public engagement, but a research methodology with many benefits.
 - Andrimo 8d: Speak to researchers in their language to reach them. A scientific communicator can do that.
 - Andrimo 8d: Show successful examples to researcher colleagues
 - Andrimo 8d: Show best practices and how other universities/research centres and their researchers are setting up citizen science activities/projects/initiatives and how they are being successful (e.g. the ones presenting at the event today).
 - Andrimo 8d: Mentoring actions to help researchers include CS as part of their research
- old school researchers**
- bureaucracy**
- Researchers in university are not evaluated according to their involvement in CS**
 - Andrimo 8d: Some researchers can be hesitant to do hands-on research with citizens. Other are critic on que quality of data provided by citizens. Or are not open to hear citizens' concerns.
 - Cristina Castracani 8d: create a database of scientific journals that are open for the publication of papers that use CS as a methodology in some way
 - Andrimo 8d: solutions: incorporation CS in science and researchers' assessment
 - Andrimo 8d: researcher evaluation criteria should be updated taking CS activities into account
 - Andrimo 8d: Recognition should be given being the university. So recognition should already come from funding agencies, as the EC is already doing. But there is need to do this at the national level.
 - Andrimo 8d: Universities can do up to a point and national policy and municipalities could support too.
- openess of researchers to investigate citizens's concerns**
- How to motivate citizens to join in our research.**
 - Andrimo 8d: Involve communication officers
 - Andrimo 8d: By preparing brochures promoting our purpose, we can direct citizens to our goal.
 - Andrimo 8d: Local or regional mapping of stakeholders (associations, NGOs...)
 - Andrimo 8d: Meetings between researchers and stakeholders
 - Cristina Castracani 8d: Involving students and secondary schools in CS projects will help universities to recruit new university students
 - Andrimo 8d: Creation of app, methodology and local project promotion
 - Andrimo 8d: Develop the sinergies with other science communication activities such European researcher's night...
- lack of method**
 - Andrimo 8d: Many researchers are unfamiliar with the methodology of working on citizen science.
- Scientists' skepticism toward CS**
- Researchers do not know how to include CS in their research**
- dedicated resources**
- Involveement in CS activities not as well-recognised as e.g. publications**
- lack of time**
- Lack of funding**
- Complete absence of CS in educational programmes**
- Not much is known about this topic yet.**
- A general confusion about the meanings of CS, public engagement and scientific divulgation among University researchers, staff and managers**
 - Andrimo 8d: Is this typical for a specific country or does this affect others?
 - Andrimo 8d: Few funding agencies dedicate funding to CS, sometimes only next to comm. & diss.
- Lack of a dedicated officer**
- where and how involve**

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What does a supportive environment for young researchers to engage with citizen science look like?

- LET OUR POWERS COMBINE!**
- Me and my brother have no problem sharing.**
- The benefits are potentially huge.**
- Community**
- Academic SUPPORT**
- A supportive environment will encourage and reward citizen science**
- Durres, Albania**
- We need to find their motivations, showcase the benefits, show the impacts...**
- supported by technology - as a tool**
- INCENTIVES**
- Not being isolated**
- Very practical, oriented to future job-life, fun to engage like a legal clinic where students can encounter citizen scientists**
- CORE VALUES**
- supported by technology - as a tool**
- network**
- HELP DESK**
- New KPIs**
Re-think how we measure success in academia
- GAMIFICATION**

:Paddle

Florence Gignac + 10 + 7d

How can the various actors specifically contribute to supporting and training early career researchers in the field of citizen science?

Academic Institutions (Universities and Research Institutions)

A qualified staff increases the quality.

valuing research through financial support.

Include citizen science in rewards, incentives

Incentivising, including public engagement practices in research evaluation, building capacity by offering specific trainings

It is a sort of a cycle. The institutional support is needed, with the help of supervisors and mentors. Connections with citizen science practitioners and other possible groups (schools, libraries, media, local administrators, museums) can create a fertile ground for growing and thriving

Training

Unis and research institutes could flag training available to new start staff, and newsletter for example could remind of resource available. Bitesize 'how to' podcasts, self-guided learning, readily available is also good to build basic knowledge

Rewarding staff's engagement in citizen science; offer spaces easily accessible to civil society in universities

Incorporating further training and support (help desk) on Citizen Science in their Graduate Centers (Graduate Academy) at the university level

Providing training
Hiring staff dedicated to support engagement between institutions and the society

Research Supervisors or mentors

Inviting them to participating in ongoing projects and related events (such as the one happening today) to build capacity, foster networking, and raising interest on the practice

Promote exchange / inviting researchers with experience citizen science to explain e.g., citizen science methodology in their colloquia

Orient early career researchers to citizen science case studies or applications when appropriate. Show them the connections with their work.

In some cases change their mindsets about citizen science and embrace it
Support Early Career Researchers
Use their networks to promote citizen science

Citizen science practitioners

Increasing networks, inviting key people from universities to join the CS communities or to events like this one, showcasing good results and impacts of ongoing projects

Be proactive in reaching universities, do not be 'scared' by academia :)

Early career researchers

Dedicate time to deepen their understanding of citizen science and build trust relationships with citizen science projects.

Policy and Decision-Making Bodies

Creating and passing laws to expand financial and structural support for researchers.

Other

RFO
Funding agencies need to provide support structures for citizen science also at an early career stage

Charity organisations

SMEs
Experts in the field can contribute to raise capacity and to the trainings

Incorporate citizen science activities in the high school curricula, so it is easier for the future

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